

Solar Adaptive Optics Simulator (SAOS): User Guide

Nicolás Rodríguez-Linares^{a,b}, José M. González-Cava^b, Luzma Montoya^a, Juan Albino Méndez-Pérez^b, Yolanda Martín^a, Adrián Calzadilla-González^a, and Miguel Núñez-Cagigal^c

^aInstituto de Astrofísica de Canarias, C/ Vía Láctea, s/n, La Laguna, 38205, Tenerife, Spain

^bDepartamento de Ingeniería Informática y de Sistemas, Universidad de La Laguna, Camino San Francisco de Paula, 19, La Laguna, 38200, Tenerife, Spain

^cEuropean Solar Telescope Fundación Canaria, 38205 La Laguna (Tenerife)

ABSTRACT

The design of Adaptive Optics (AO) systems relies heavily on simulation platforms to evaluate performance prior to construction and integration. Given the complexity of AO systems, modifying components after deployment is particularly challenging. Over the past decades, several open-source AO simulation platforms have been developed to support the community, though no universal standard exists due to the specific requirements of each application. Moreover, building a new simulator is a significant undertaking, often beyond the scope of many AO teams worldwide.

SAOS builds upon the object-oriented architecture of OOPAO (originally derived from OOMAO), restructuring its design to center around individual lines of sight rather than a central telescope class. This allows for better scalability and more efficient parallel handling of extended objects.

Additional features include modules for testing various reconstruction algorithms and control strategies, as well as a software interface based on ZeroMQ. This enables users to integrate custom GUIs and data logging workflows. SAOS also provides a built-in GUI for convenience.

Keywords: SAOS, Solar AO, Simulations, Python

1. INTRODUCTION

Adaptive optics systems are essential for ground-based observations, enabling compensation of atmospheric turbulence and allowing telescopes to approach their diffraction limit.

Numerical simulations play a key role in the design and validation of AO systems, allowing different configurations to be tested prior to implementation. In the solar case, a critical requirement for physical accuracy is the proper modeling of the extended field of view. Each point on the Sun propagates through a different region of atmospheric turbulence, acquiring a distinct phase. This anisoplanatic effect degrades the quality of the wavefront measurements and constitutes a significant source of error, which must be accurately represented to avoid overestimating AO system performance.

Several AO simulation platforms have been developed over the past decades, each targeting specific applications. However, most existing tools are focused on night-time AO and are not well suited for solar simulations, which require dedicated extended source modeling and efficient handling of multiple directions.

Further author information:

Send correspondence to N.R.L.: nicolas.linares@iac.es

In this context, SAOS [5] has been developed as a modular and flexible framework tailored for solar AO simulations. The simulator is implemented in Python and follows an object-oriented architecture, where optical components are defined as independent modules and optical propagation is managed through Light Path objects. This design enables efficient parallelization and simplifies the configuration of complex AO systems.

SAOS builds upon OOPAO [4], a recent Python-based AO simulator that adopts a modular class-based approach, where each optical element is represented as an independent component. This architecture is extended in SAOS by introducing the Light Path abstraction, which organizes the propagation of light through the system. The object-oriented paradigm itself originates from OOMAO [3], a MATLAB-based simulator.

Previous solar AO simulation efforts have typically been implemented as extensions of night-time AO platforms, where the treatment of extended sources is incorporated after the core design. This is the case for DASP [1] and CAOS [2]. While these simulators provide strong performance for SCAO configurations, they present limitations in flexibility and scalability when addressing more complex systems such as MCAO.

This document is structured as a practical tutorial aimed at guiding the user through the main features of SAOS. Section 2 introduces the overall architecture of the simulator and its execution workflow. Section 3 describes the available modules and their configuration. Section 4 presents a complete SCAO example combining extended and point-like sources. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions and discusses possible extensions.

2. SAOS ARCHITECTURE

SAOS is designed as a modular and extensible simulation framework for AO systems. Its architecture follows an object-oriented approach in which each physical component of the system is represented by an independent module, while the optical propagation is managed through a set of Light Path instances.

The core design principle of SAOS is the separation between system components and data flow. Optical elements such as the atmosphere, telescope, deformable mirrors, wavefront sensors, and science cameras are implemented as stateless processing units. These modules do not store transient simulation data, which is instead handled by the Light Path objects. This design avoids shared state across components and enables efficient parallel execution.

The simulation workflow is organized as an iterative loop, where each iteration represents a single time step of the AO system. The main steps of the simulation are:

1. **Atmosphere update:** the atmospheric phase screens are advanced in time according to the wind profiles of each layer. This process is parallelized per layer.
2. **Light propagation:** each Light Path propagates the optical field through the system. This includes the contribution of the atmosphere, deformable mirrors, and optional aberrations. The propagation also produces the wavefront sensor measurements and science camera images. Multiple Light Path instances can be executed concurrently, enabling efficient multi-direction and multi-wavelength simulations.
3. **Wavefront reconstruction and control:** the controller processes the measurements from the wavefront sensors, together with the reconstruction matrix, to compute the corrective commands applied to the deformable mirrors.
4. **Deformable mirror update:** the shape of each deformable mirror is updated according to the computed commands.
5. **Data handling:** simulation data can be streamed in real time through the Sharepoint module and/or stored using the Savepoint module for offline analysis.

A key feature of SAOS is the use of Light Paths as the central abstraction for optical propagation. Each Light Path represents an independent line of sight and contains all the data buffers associated with the propagation, including intermediate phases, optical path differences (OPDs), wavefront sensor measurements, and science images. This allows different branches of the system—such as sensing and evaluation paths—to be simulated simultaneously without interference.

The architecture naturally supports parallelization at multiple levels. Atmospheric layers can be updated independently, and Light Paths can be propagated concurrently without shared memory conflicts. Additionally, selected modules such as the wavefront sensor and science camera can leverage GPU acceleration when available.

This modular and data-centric design enables SAOS to scale from simple single-conjugate AO (SCAO) configurations to more complex systems such as ground-layer AO (GLAO) and multi-conjugate AO (MCAO), while maintaining a consistent and flexible workflow.

Figure 1 illustrates the general workflow of the simulation loop with multiple Light Path instances, following the processing steps described above.

Figure 1. Illustration of the Light Path architecture, showing multiple propagation branches for sensing and science channels.

3. MODULES

The modules available in SAOS implement the optical and processing elements of an AO system. Each module is defined as a software class initialized with the optical properties of the corresponding element. These classes act as processing units and do not store transient buffers from the AO simulation, enabling efficient parallelization through multithreading without requiring multiple instances with identical parameters.

Data buffers generated during light propagation are managed by Light Path instances, which are the core abstract classes responsible for handling optical propagation across the different elements.

Additional details on performance, validation, and algorithm implementation can be found in [5].

3.1 Telescope

The telescope is the central element of an AO system. It is primarily defined by its pupil diameter, expressed in meters. The pupil may include a central obscuration, specified as a fraction of the primary pupil diameter. In addition, the telescope field of view (FoV), given in arcseconds, must be defined to establish the maximum observable field, which is used for internal consistency checks within the simulation.

The Telescope module also defines the temporal sampling of the AO system through the sampling time, which sets the simulation time step and establishes the temporal scale of the simulation. Furthermore, the spatial resolution is controlled by the *resolution* parameter. The pupil is discretized into a square grid of $nPoints \times nPoints$, defining the sampling of the atmospheric phase screens and thus the maximum spatial frequencies represented in the turbulence. This sampling also affects the resolution within the wavefront sensor subapertures, which is particularly relevant in solar AO systems, where projection effects at different atmospheric layers can degrade measurement quality.

Typically, the resolution is chosen as a multiple of the number of wavefront sensor subapertures. Increasing this parameter improves spatial fidelity but also increases memory usage and computational cost. In most cases,

a factor of 4 relative to the number of subapertures provides a good balance, while a factor of 6 is recommended for more demanding scenarios, such as noise characterization in solar simulations.

The following code snippet shows an example of how to configure the EST telescope:

Listing 1. Telescope instance

```
1 diameter = 4.149 # in [m]
2 obs_diameter = 1.3 # in [m]
3 sampling_time = 1/2000 # in [s]
4 n_subaperture = 36
5 resolution = n_subaperture * 4 # phase screen resolution in [px]
6 pixel_size = diameter / resolution
7 tel_fov = 60 # in [arcsec]
8
9 est_tel = Telescope(diameter=diameter,
10                   resolution=resolution,
11                   centralObstruction=obs_diameter / diameter,
12                   samplingTime=sampling_time,
13                   fov=tel_fov,
14                   logger=test_logger.logger)
```

The telescope structure may also include spiders, defined by the width of the support legs (in meters) and their angular positions. For example, a four-leg spider can be configured as follows:

Listing 2. Adding a spider

```
1 spider_angle = [0, 90, 180, 270] # in degrees
2 spider_thickness = 0.060 # in [m]
3
4 est_tel.apply_spiders(spider_angle, spider_thickness)
```

3.2 Sources

Sources represent the incoming light entering the AO system. In SAOS, two source models are available: point sources and extended sources.

Point sources are typically used to represent natural guide stars or unresolved science targets in night-time AO simulations. They are defined by their magnitude, optical band, and angular coordinates in the field. These coordinates are provided in polar form, with the radius in arcseconds and the angle in degrees.

The following example shows how to define two point-like guide stars in different spectral bands:

Listing 3. Point-like sources

```
1 ngs_vis = Source(magnitude=5,
2                 optBand='V0',
3                 coordinates=[0, 0],
4                 logger=test_logger.logger)
5
6 ngs_red = Source(magnitude=5,
7                 optBand='R4',
8                 coordinates=[0, 0],
9                 logger=test_logger.logger)
```

Extended sources are intended for objects such as the Sun. In this case, the source is sampled over multiple angular directions within the sensed field of view (FoV), referred to internally as subdirections. This allows the simulation to reproduce the fact that each point of the extended source propagates through a different region of the atmosphere, thus capturing anisoplanatism effects.

In addition to the point source parameters, an extended source must define the number of subdirections. The FoV is sampled using a grid of $nSubDirs \times nSubDirs$. Typically, a value of 3 is sufficient; however, to ensure adequate sampling, the required number should be derived from the isoplanatic angle of the simulated atmospheric profile. The number of subdirections has a strong impact on performance, as it increases the number of internal correlations and projections.

Furthermore, the model requires defining both the subdirection margin and the patch padding. The extended source may shift due to tip-tilt effects, which can introduce undefined regions into the FoV. To avoid this artifact, padding is added to ensure that a sufficiently large source patch is available before cropping, guaranteeing that the observed FoV always contains meaningful information. Padding values must be provided in arcseconds.

Listing 4. Extended sources

```

1 sun_vis = ExtendedSource(optBand='V',
2                          coordinates=[0, 0],
3                          nSubDirs=3,
4                          fov=9.975,
5                          subDir_margin=4.0,
6                          patch_padding=5.0,
7                          logger=test_logger.logger)
8
9 sun_red = ExtendedSource(optBand='R',
10                         coordinates=[0, 0],
11                         nSubDirs=3,
12                         fov=9.269,
13                         subDir_margin=4.0,
14                         patch_padding=5.0,
15                         logger=test_logger.logger)

```

3.3 Atmosphere

The Atmosphere module models the turbulent layers traversed by the incoming wavefront. The turbulence is represented by a discrete set of layers, each defined by its altitude, in meters; relative strength; wind speed, in meters per second; and wind direction, in degrees.

The overall seeing conditions are controlled by the Fried parameter r_0 and the outer scale L_0 . The Fried parameter must be specified at zenith and at a wavelength of 500 nm.

The fractional contribution of each layer determines how the turbulence is distributed vertically. In addition, the zenith angle can be used to project the turbulence to the zenith angle of the telescope, accounting for the r_0 and layer altitude variations.

The following example illustrates the definition of a five-layer atmosphere:

Listing 5. Atmosphere definition

```

1 atm = Atmosphere(r0=0.09,
2                 L0=25,
3                 fractionalR0=[0.53, 0.37, 0.05, 0.03, 0.02],
4                 altitude=[100, 1500, 5000, 10000, 15000],
5                 windDirection=[45, 90, 180, 67, 2],
6                 windSpeed=[12, 4, 45, 18, 8],
7                 telescope=est_tel,
8                 zenith=15,
9                 logger=test_logger.logger)

```

The atmosphere can either be generated from scratch or loaded from a previously stored realization. This is useful when reproducibility is required:

Listing 6. Generating or loading atmospheric phase screens

```

1 if generate_new_atm:
2     atm.initializeAtmosphere()
3     atm.save(save_filename_atm)
4 else:
5     atm.load(load_filename_atm)

```

During the simulation loop, the atmosphere is advanced in time according to the wind profiles of the different layers:

Listing 7. Atmosphere temporal update

```

1 atm.update()

```

3.4 Shack-Hartmann Wavefront Sensor

The Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor (SH-WFS) measures local wavefront slopes by dividing the pupil into subapertures. Within each subaperture, the local tip-tilt of the wavefront is estimated from the displacement of the corresponding spot image.

SAOS provides two variants of this sensor. The classical SH-WFS is designed for point-like sources, as typically used in night-time AO systems. For solar AO, a correlating SH-WFS is implemented, where local displacements are estimated via image cross-correlation rather than direct centroiding.

In both cases, a center-of-gravity (CoG) algorithm is used to compute the spot position. The CoG is applied to a selection of the brightest pixels within each subaperture, as controlled by the *use_brightest* parameter. In the correlating SH-WFS, the CoG is computed on the correlation image, which generally exhibits low contrast between the peak and the background. As a result, relatively small values of *use_brightest* (typically around 9 pixels) are recommended.

The main configuration parameters include the number of subapertures, the plate scale (in pixels per arcsecond), and the field of view (FoV) assigned to each subaperture (in arcseconds). Additional parameters, such as guard pixels and correlation oversampling, can be used to improve robustness and reduce edge effects.

For night-time AO, the SH-WFS can be instantiated as follows:

Listing 8. Shack-Hartmann for night-time AO

```
1 vis_night_wfs = ShackHartmann(telescope=est_tel,
2                               src=ngs_vis,
3                               lightRatio=0.9,
4                               nSubap=50,
5                               plate_scale=0.475,
6                               fieldOfView=9.975,
7                               guardPx=2,
8                               fft_fieldOfView_oversampling=0.5,
9                               use_brightest=50,
10                              unit_in_rad=False,
11                              logger=test_logger.logger)
```

For solar AO, a correlating SH-WFS can be defined as follows:

Listing 9. Correlating Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor

```
1 red_wfs = CorrelatingShackHartmann(telescope=est_tel,
2                                     src=sun_red,
3                                     lightRatio=0.9,
4                                     nSubap=36,
5                                     plate_scale=0.403,
6                                     fieldOfView=9.269,
7                                     guardPx=2,
8                                     fft_fieldOfView_oversampling=0.5,
9                                     use_brightest=9,
10                                    unit_in_rad=False,
11                                    logger=test_logger.logger)
```

3.5 Deformable mirror

Deformable mirrors (DMs) are the active correcting elements of the AO system. They introduce a controlled phase pattern to compensate for the optical aberrations measured by the wavefront sensor.

A deformable mirror is usually defined by the number of actuators, the actuator geometry, and its conjugation altitude, in meters. In SAOS, both Cartesian and Radial actuator layouts are supported. Optionally, a dynamic model can be associated with the mirror to simulate temporal response behaviour.

The following example defines two mirrors with different actuator samplings:

Listing 10. Deformable mirrors definition

```
1 radial_mirror_params = {'dynamicModel': 'models/asm_discrete_model.h5'}
2 cartesian_mirror_params = {'dynamicModel': 'models/m7_discrete_model.h5'}
3
```

```

4 radial_mirror = DeformableMirror(telescope=est_tel,
5                                 nActs=37,
6                                 altitude=0,
7                                 typeDM='radial',
8                                 logger=test_logger.logger,
9                                 **radial_mirror_params)
10
11 cartesian_mirror = DeformableMirror(telescope=est_tel,
12                                    nActs=51,
13                                    altitude=0,
14                                    typeDM='cartesian',
15                                    logger=test_logger.logger,
16                                    **cartesian_mirror_params)

```

Multiple mirrors can then be grouped into a list and used sequentially within the same optical path:

Listing 11. Grouping deformable mirrors

```

1 dms = [radial_mirror, cartesian_mirror]

```

Once the control action has been computed, the mirror surfaces are updated at each simulation step:

Listing 12. Updating the deformable mirror commands

```

1 for j in range(len(dms)):
2     dms[j].updateDMShape(cmd[j])

```

3.6 Science Camera

The science camera represents the final detector where the corrected image is formed. It integrates the propagated optical field over a given exposure time and produces the scientific image used for performance assessment.

Its main parameters include the field of view (FoV), in arcseconds; the plate scale, in pixels per arcsecond; the integration time, in seconds; and the detector sampling time, also in seconds. Detector noise can optionally be enabled to simulate realistic acquisition conditions.

The following example shows the definition of one science camera:

Listing 13. Science cameras

```

1 vis_scicam = ScienceCam(fieldOfView=9.975,
2                          plate_scale=0.0128,
3                          samplingTime=est_tel.samplingTime,
4                          telescope=est_tel,
5                          integrationTime=1./scienceFs,
6                          noiseFlag=False,
7                          logger=test_logger.logger)

```

Science cameras are independent of the source type. The module internally identifies the source model and generates the appropriate science image for both point-like and extended sources.

In many practical cases, the science camera operates at a lower frame rate than the AO loop, integrating multiple AO iterations into a single exposure. This behavior is controlled by the integration time.

If the integration time is not an integer multiple of the sampling time, fractional contributions are accounted for in the photon integration. However, the phase is not evaluated at sub-sampling intervals, meaning that the minimum temporal resolution of the phase remains limited by the sampling time.

3.7 Light Path

The Light Path is the main abstraction responsible for orchestrating optical propagation through the different modules. It connects the source, atmosphere, telescope, deformable mirrors, wavefront sensor, optional vibration models, non-common path aberrations (NCPAs), and science camera into a consistent propagation chain.

Each Light Path defines one branch of the system. This is particularly useful when simulating multiple wavelengths, sensing channels, or evaluation paths in parallel. For example, one branch can be used for wavefront sensing with an extended source, while another evaluates image quality using a point-like source.

The following example creates a red sensing branch:

Listing 14. Red sensing Light Path

```

1 red_path = LightPath(test_logger.logger)
2 red_path.initialize_path(src=sun_red,
3                         atm=atm,
4                         tel=est_tel,
5                         dm=radial_mirror,
6                         wfs=red_wfs,
7                         vibration=None,
8                         sci=red_scicam,
9                         delay=1)

```

A visible branch can be defined in a similar way, here using two deformable mirrors:

Listing 15. Visible sensing Light Path

```

1 vis_path = LightPath(test_logger.logger)
2 vis_path.initialize_path(src=sun_vis,
3                         atm=atm,
4                         tel=est_tel,
5                         dm=[radial_mirror, cartesian_mirror],
6                         wfs=vis_wfs,
7                         vibration=None,
8                         sci=vis_scicam,
9                         delay=2)

```

Evaluation branches can also be defined without a wavefront sensor, for instance to assess corrected scientific performance on a point-like source:

Listing 16. Evaluation Light Path without WFS

```

1 eval_path = LightPath(test_logger.logger)
2 eval_path.initialize_path(src=ngs_vis,
3                          atm=atm,
4                          tel=est_tel,
5                          dm=[radial_mirror, cartesian_mirror],
6                          wfs=None,
7                          vibration=None,
8                          sci=vis_scicam,
9                          delay=2)

```

The *delay* parameter, defined in discrete simulation steps, introduces a pure latency in the control loop. It models the delay between wavefront measurement and correction that is inherently present in real AO systems.

All data buffers associated with the propagation are stored within each Light Path instance. These include intermediate phase, optical path differences, wavefront sensor frames, science camera images, wavefront measurements, and deformable mirror commands.

This design avoids shared state between propagation branches, allowing Light Path instances to be executed in parallel without restrictions and ensuring thread-safe operation without memory access conflicts.

3.8 Interaction Matrix

The interaction matrix (IM) describes the response of the wavefront sensor to known perturbations applied to the deformable mirrors. It is a key component for wavefront reconstruction and the computation of the control law.

In SAOS, the interaction matrix is managed through the *InteractionMatrixHandler* class. This class automatically initializes the interaction matrix structure from the defined Light Path instances, and provides methods to load a modal basis, measure a new matrix, or load a precomputed one from disk.

The following example shows a typical initialization:

Listing 17. Interaction matrix handler

```

1 im_handler = InteractionMatrixHandler(test_logger.logger)
2 im_handler.initialize_im_class(scao_light_path_list)

```

A modal basis can be loaded prior to measuring the interaction matrix:

Listing 18. Loading a modal basis

```
1 im_handler.load_modalBasis(load_filename_modalBasis)
```

The interaction matrix is then measured by applying modal perturbations with a given stroke amplitude:

Listing 19. Measuring the interaction matrix

```
1 im_handler.measure(modal_basis='dh',
2                   stroke=[1e-6, 7.5e-7],
3                   nModes=None)
```

Several modal bases are available, including Zernike, Karhunen–Loève, disc-harmonic, Hadamard, and zonal modes. The stroke can be configured independently for each deformable mirror, following the order defined in the Light Path. The stroke values are expressed in meters.

It is important to note that the stroke is defined with respect to the entrance pupil diameter. Therefore, when transferring a simulated interaction matrix to a real system, the deformable mirror commands must be properly scaled according to the effective pupil size at the mirror.

The number of modes can be set for each DM or set to None, which uses the number of actuators to set the number of modes.

Finally, the resulting matrix can be stored for later reuse:

Listing 20. Saving the interaction matrix

```
1 im_handler.save_IM(save_filename_IM)
2 im_handler.save_modalBasis(save_filename_modalBasis)
```

If the interaction matrix is already available, it can be loaded directly:

Listing 21. Loading a precomputed interaction matrix

```
1 im_handler.load_IM(load_filename_IM)
```

3.9 Controller

The Controller computes the corrective action from the wavefront sensor measurements and the interaction matrix, and is therefore responsible for closing the AO loop.

The reconstruction process can be configured through the *reconstructionMethod* argument, which supports two options: *inversion* and *tikhonov*.

The *inversion* method performs a pseudo-inverse of the interaction matrix defined between each deformable mirror and the associated wavefront sensors. Noise filtering is controlled through the *rcond* parameter, which truncates singular values below a given threshold relative to the maximum singular value.

The *tikhonov* method implements Tikhonov regularization, where the filtering is governed by the *beta* parameter. This parameter scales the squared maximum singular value and controls the trade-off between noise amplification and reconstruction accuracy.

The control strategy is specified by the *controllerType* argument. The available options are *leaky*, *forwardPI*, and *backwardPI*, corresponding to a leaky integrator, a proportional-integral (PI) controller using Forward Euler discretization, and a PI controller using Backward Euler discretization, respectively.

The leaky integrator requires the definition of the *gain* and *decay* parameters for each DM. The PI controllers use the *gain* as the proportional term and *ki* as the integral gain.

A typical controller configuration is:

Listing 22. Controller definition

```
1 controller_kwargs = {'rcond': 0.025,
2                   'beta': 1e-4,
3                   'gain': [0.2, 0.10],
4                   'decay': [0.99, 0.99],
5                   'ki': [0.0, 0.0]}
```

```

6 controller = Controller(telescope=est_tel,
7                       interactionMatrix=im_handler,
8                       reconstructionMethod='tikhonov',
9                       controllerType='leaky',
10                      logger=test_logger.logger,
11                      **controller_kwargs)
12

```

At each simulation step, the controller processes the current Light Path instances and computes the commands to be applied to the deformable mirrors:

Listing 23. Computing the control action

```

1 cmd = controller.computeControlAction(scao_light_path_list)

```

3.10 Savepoint

The Savepoint module provides persistent storage for simulation outputs. It can be configured to store different data products, such as atmospheric states, deformable mirror commands, wavefront sensor measurements, and science frames.

This module is particularly useful for long simulations where only a subset of the generated data needs to be retained for post-processing. It also supports storing only summary metrics to reduce storage requirements.

The available buffers include the atmospheric phase screens per layer (*atm*); the atmosphere projected along each source direction (*atm_per_dir*), including subdirection data for extended sources; the deformable mirror commands (*dm*); the DM phase projected per direction and subdirection (*dm_per_dir*); wavefront sensor slope measurements in both 1D and 2D formats (*slopes*); the WFS frames (*wfs_frame*); the phase and optical path difference at the WFS pupil (*wfs*); and the phase and OPD at the science camera (*sci*).

Each argument acts as a decimation factor. A value of 0 disables both buffer storage and metric computation, while a value greater than 0 stores one out of every N samples (e.g., a value of 1 stores all samples).

The *only_metrics* flag applies to all enabled buffers and stores only per-step summary statistics. For phase and OPD, the stored metrics include the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation over the pupil mask. The same statistics are computed for slopes and DM commands. For science images, the Strehl ratio is computed for point-like sources, while contrast and MFGS are computed for extended sources.

A typical Savepoint configuration is:

Listing 24. Savepoint definition

```

1 savepoint = Savepoint(file_path='',
2                      atm=1,
3                      atm_per_dir=1,
4                      dm=1,
5                      dm_per_dir=1,
6                      slopes=1,
7                      wfs=1,
8                      wfs_frame=1,
9                      sci=1,
10                     sci_frame=1,
11                     only_metrics=1,
12                     logger=test_logger.logger)

```

During the simulation loop, the selected data can be stored as follows:

Listing 25. Saving simulation data

```

1 savepoint.save([atm], i)
2 savepoint.save(dms, i)
3 savepoint.save(scao_light_path_list, i)

```

3.11 Sharepoint

The Sharepoint module enables real-time data exchange with external clients, such as graphical user interfaces or monitoring tools, using ZeroMQ. It exposes selected simulation products while the AO loop is running, allowing online inspection without interfering with the simulation workflow.

The user can select which quantities are published. The available buffers are the same as those defined in the Savepoint module.

The following example shows a typical Sharepoint initialization:

Listing 26. Sharepoint definition

```
1 sharepoint = Sharepoint(test_logger.logger,  
2     port=5573,  
3     atm=1,  
4     atm_per_dir=0,  
5     dm=1,  
6     dm_per_dir=0,  
7     slopes=1,  
8     wfs=1,  
9     wfs_frame=1,  
10    sci=1,  
11    sci_frame=1)
```

The Sharepoint module follows the same logic as the Savepoint module, where each argument defines a decimation factor for the corresponding buffer. The *port* parameter specifies the TCP port used for data exchange. Optionally, the target IP address and communication protocol can also be configured, with default values set to localhost and TCP, respectively.

Once configured, data can be streamed at each simulation step:

Listing 27. Sharing data during the simulation

```
1 sharepoint.shareData(scao_light_path_list, i, [atm], dms)
```

4. EXAMPLES

The official SAOS repository is hosted on [GitHub](#). The project follows a release-based versioning scheme to consolidate major improvements into stable versions. This tutorial is based on release v4.0.0, which includes the modules described in this article along with several bug fixes.

In addition to the source code, the repository provides a **tutorial** directory containing several representative use cases. These examples are intended as a guide for users to build their own simulations. The available tutorials include: (i) an SCAO configuration using an extended source for correction and a point-like source for performance evaluation; and (ii) two MCAO configurations with seven sources and three deformable mirrors (DMs), covering both point-like and solar cases.

This section introduces the key elements of these examples, together with representative GUI results illustrating the capabilities of SAOS.

4.1 SCAO example: extended-source correction with point-like source evaluation

In solar adaptive optics, there is no direct image quality metric equivalent to the Strehl ratio used in night-time AO. To assess performance in simulations, it is common to evaluate the correction using a point-like source, enabling the computation of the Strehl ratio. However, the correction itself must be performed using an extended source to properly account for anisoplanatic effects.

A typical workflow consists of: (i) running the AO loop with an extended source to obtain a realistic residual phase, and (ii) propagating this residual phase through a point-like source path to evaluate image-quality metrics offline.

In SAOS, this is implemented by defining two Light Paths: - a **correction path**, including an extended source and a WFS, where the control loop is closed; - an **evaluation path**, sharing the same optical elements (telescope, DMs, geometry), but using a point-like source and no WFS, evaluated online.

The following listing shows how this can be implemented. Two AO channels (visible and red) are defined, each with its own correction and evaluation paths.

Listing 28. Dual-source SCAO example

```

1  ## Build the Light Path
2
3  scao_light_path_list = []
4
5  # Create red branch
6  scao_light_path_list.append(LightPath(test_logger.logger))
7  scao_light_path_list[-1].initialize_path(
8      src=sun_red,
9      atm=atm,
10     tel=est_tel,
11     dm=dms[0],
12     wfs=red_wfs,
13     vibration=red_vibrations,
14     sci=red_scicam,
15     delay=1
16 )
17
18 # Create vis branch
19 scao_light_path_list.append(LightPath(test_logger.logger))
20 scao_light_path_list[-1].initialize_path(
21     src=sun_vis,
22     atm=atm,
23     tel=est_tel,
24     dm=dms,
25     wfs=vis_wfs,
26     vibration=red_vibrations,
27     sci=vis_scicam,
28     delay=2
29 )
30
31 # Red branch evaluation point-like source
32 scao_light_path_list.append(LightPath(test_logger.logger))
33 scao_light_path_list[-1].initialize_path(
34     src=ngs_red,
35     atm=atm,
36     tel=est_tel,
37     dm=dms[0],
38     wfs=None,
39     vibration=red_vibrations,
40     sci=red_scicam,
41     delay=1
42 )
43
44 # Visible branch evaluation point-like source
45 scao_light_path_list.append(LightPath(test_logger.logger))
46 scao_light_path_list[-1].initialize_path(
47     src=ngs_vis,
48     atm=atm,
49     tel=est_tel,
50     dm=dms,
51     wfs=None,
52     vibration=vis_vibrations,
53     sci=vis_scicam,
54     delay=2
55 )
56
57 lightPathTasks = []
58 for i in range(len(scao_light_path_list)):
59     lightPathTasks.append(delayed(scao_light_path_list[i].propagate)(True))

```

The different buffers can be visualized using a custom-made GUI that subscribes to the topics published by Sharepoint via ZeroMQ. For instance, Figure 2 shows several buffers: input atmosphere, visible WFS slopes in

2D, ASM shape, and visible science images for both point-like and extended sources.

Figure 2. SCAO example: (top-left) WFS slope measurements; (top-right) science image of an extended source; (bottom-left) M7 deformable mirror surface; (bottom-right) science image of a point-like source.

4.2 MCAO example: seven point-like sources

MCAO systems require multiple sensing directions to adequately sample the three-dimensional structure of atmospheric turbulence. Additionally, MCAO architectures incorporate several deformable mirrors, each conjugated to different altitude planes, providing sufficient degrees of freedom to correct turbulence along multiple lines of sight.

SAOS natively supports MCAO configurations without requiring complex modifications. Each sensing direction is implemented as an independent Light Path, where the only difference between paths is the source coordinates. Typically, all wavefront sensors operate at the same wavelength and share identical optical parameters (e.g., field of view and plate scale). Therefore, within SAOS, it is sufficient to define a single WFS instance, as modules act as stateless processing units; the simulation state is instead contained within the Light Path instances.

To define seven sensing directions using point-like sources, the following example creates a list of stars distributed across a field of view of 30 arcseconds:

Listing 29. Defining multiple sensing directions

```

1 # On axis
2 # 6 NGS circularly distributed at a radius of 15" and rotated by 45 degrees
3 coord_list = [[0, 0]] + [[15, i * 360 / 6 + 45] for i in range(6)]
4
5 ngs_list = []
6
7 for i in range(len(coord_list)):
8     ngs_list.append(Source(magnitude = 5,
9                           optBand = 'R4',
10                          coordinates=coord_list[i],
11                          logger=test_logger.logger))

```

The corresponding Light Paths are initialized as follows:

Listing 30. Initializing MCAO Light Paths

```

1  ## Build the Light Path
2
3  scao_light_path_list = []
4
5  # Create red branch
6  for i in range(len(ngs_list)):
7      if (i == 0) or (i == 2) or (i == 6): # Add science camera
8          scao_light_path_list.append(LightPath(test_logger.logger))
9          scao_light_path_list[-1].initialize_path(src=ngs_list[i], atm=atm, tel=est_tel, dm=dms, wfs=
10             red_wfs, vibration=red_vibrations, sci=red_scicam, delay=0)
11         else:
12             scao_light_path_list.append(LightPath(test_logger.logger))
13             scao_light_path_list[-1].initialize_path(src=ngs_list[i], atm=atm, tel=est_tel, dm=dms, wfs=
14                 red_wfs, vibration=red_vibrations, sci=None, delay=0)
15
16 scao_light_path_list.append(LightPath(test_logger.logger))
17 scao_light_path_list[-1].initialize_path(src=ext_sci_ngs, atm=atm, tel=est_tel, dm=dms, wfs=None,
18     vibration=red_vibrations, sci=red_scicam, delay=0)
19
20 lightPathTasks = []
21 for i in range(len(scao_light_path_list)):
22     lightPathTasks.append(delayed(scao_light_path_list[i].propagate)(True))

```

This configuration defines multiple sensing directions, complemented by additional science channels. During execution, each Light Path maintains its own internal buffers, which can be accessed and visualized through a client GUI, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. MCAO example: (top-left) atmospheric phase screen at layer 3; (top-right) WFS slope map for Light Path 2; (bottom-left) science image from Light Path 0; (bottom-right) WFS detector frame from Light Path 3.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This article has presented a practical tutorial of SAOS, a modular simulator designed to support the development and validation of solar adaptive optics systems. The workflow and examples show how SAOS can be configured

from simple SCAO setups to more demanding MCAO scenarios, while maintaining a consistent architecture based on independent modules and Light Path instances.

The presented use cases highlight two key strengths of the platform: realistic modeling of extended solar sources for wavefront sensing, and flexible evaluation pipelines for performance analysis using point-like references. Together with its support for real-time data sharing and structured data logging, SAOS provides a robust environment for algorithm testing, controller tuning, and end-to-end AO studies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge the use of OpenAI GPT-5 for the language and grammar clean-up of the article.

This work was supported by MICIN, the European Union NextGenerationEU and the RTRP under Grant number ICTS2022-007828. Additionally, it was supported by Agencia Estatal de Investigación del Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (MCIN/AEI) and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) under Grant number PID2021-126118NB-I00/10.13039/501100011033.

Moreover, the project was supported by the Canary Islands Government under the Grant file SD 17/01. Furthermore, it was supported by MCIN/AEI and ERDF under Grant number IAC-12 and Grant number IACA16-BE-3955. Finally, it also received support from European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant number 824135.

References

- [1] A.G. Basden et al. “The Durham Adaptive Optics Simulation Platform (DASP): Current status”. In: *SoftwareX* 7 (2018), pp. 63–69. ISSN: 2352-7110. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2018.02.005>. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352711018300232>.
- [2] Marcel Carbillet et al. “CAOS: a numerical simulation tool for astronomical adaptive optics (and beyond)”. In: *Advancements in Adaptive Optics*. Ed. by Domenico Bonaccini Calia, Brent L. Ellerbroek, and Roberto Ragazzoni. Vol. 5490. International Society for Optics and Photonics. SPIE, 2004, pp. 637–648. DOI: [10.1117/12.551552](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.551552). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.551552>.
- [3] R. Conan and C. Correia. “Object-oriented Matlab adaptive optics toolbox”. In: *Adaptive Optics Systems IV*. Ed. by Enrico Marchetti, Laird M. Close, and Jean-Pierre Vran. Vol. 9148. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. Aug. 2014, 91486C, p. 91486C. DOI: [10.1117/12.2054470](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2054470).
- [4] Cedric Taissir Heritier, Christophe Verinaud, and Carlos M. Correia. “OOPAO: Object Oriented Python Adaptive Optics”. In: *Adaptive Optics for Extremely Large Telescopes 7th Edition*. ONERA. Avignon, France, June 2023. DOI: [10.13009/A04ELT7-2023-052](https://doi.org/10.13009/A04ELT7-2023-052). URL: <https://hal.science/hal-04402878>.
- [5] Nicolás Rodríguez-Linares et al. “SAOS: Solar Adaptive Optics Simulator”. In: *Journal of Astronomical Telescopes, Instruments, and Systems* (2026). Submitted.